

Analysis of trace levels of toxic sodium monochloroacetate in alkylamidobetaines by HPLC[†]

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Trace levels of sodium monochloroacetate (SMCA) in an amphoteric surfactant cocoamidopropylbetaine (CAPB), have been analyzed by HPLC. SMCA is isolated from the surfactant matrix by solid phase extraction and then converted into an UV-absorbing derivative by quaternizing *p*-methoxycinnamidopropyldimethylamine.

Alkylbetaines in general and cocoamidopropylbetaine (CAPB, **1**) in particular are known for their mildness and hence are very widely used in personal care and consumer products¹. As a result of their superior performance, biodegradability and low toxicological profile, they are used on huge scale in cosmetic industry²⁻¹⁰.

CAPB is made by a two-step synthesis^{2,5,7}. In the first step, cocofatty acid ($R = C_8$ to C_{18}) is reacted with *N,N*-dimethylpropyldiamine (DMAPA) to give the alkylamidopropyldimethylamine. The tertiary amino group of this amidoamine intermediate is then quaternized by reacting with sodium salt of monochloroacetic acid (SMCA) in aqueous medium to afford the betaine surfactant of 28% (w/w) active matter. Since at no stage purification is performed, this tremendously popular cosmetic surfactant invariably has trace levels of both free DMAPA¹¹ and SMCA¹² as impurities that are quite toxic. We have already reported analysis of traces of DMAPA by ion-exchange chromatography¹³.

Similarly, logical choice for estimating SMCA in a surfactant solution would be ion-exchange chromatography. However, ion-exchange chromatography can not be performed on conventional HPLC because the mobile phases employed are usually quite acidic or basic. Special ion chromatographs are available for this purpose that are made up of polyether ether ketone (PEEK) that is resistant to both acids and bases. A couple of methods based on gas chroma-

tography are reported, which involve derivatization of SMCA into its ethyl ester and then it is either isolated by solvent extraction¹⁴ or by head space device¹⁵ for injecting into a capillary column. Unfortunately, in our hands these methods did not work satisfactorily. This failure actually prompted us to develop the method based on conventional HPLC.

Results and discussion

For isolation of SMCA from surfactant matrix there were two options, (i) liquid-liquid extraction¹⁶ and (ii) solid phase extraction¹⁷. There are excellent liquid-liquid extraction systems reported to extract surfactants quantitatively from their aqueous solutions. However, while doing so partial loss of free SMCA into organic layer was observed. This could be due to SMCA getting trapped inside the reverse micelles of surfactant molecules. Nevertheless, the use of solid phase extraction proved to be quite clean and quantitative.

The derivatizing reagent, *p*-methoxycinnamidopropyldimethylamine (**2**) was synthesized by reacting primary amino group of *N,N*-dimethylpropyldiamine either with *p*-methoxycinnamic acid or its ester¹⁸ or its acid chloride. It was obtained as white crystalline solid (m.p. 80°). It gave satisfactory elemental analysis. The extended conjugation of this molecule is reflected in its molar extinction coefficient of 24000 at 298 nm. Its IR spectrum showed characteristic carbonyl of amide at 1660 and NH stretchings at 3300 cm^{-1} . Its ¹H and ¹³C NMR were in complete agreement with the assigned structure (see Experimental). It is clear from its structure that the molecule is hydrolytically stable for quaternization reactions that are often performed in aqueous solvents.

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To make standard betaine for chromatographic analysis, the quaternization of *p*-methoxycinnamidopropyl-dimethylamine by sodium monochloroacetate is performed in aqueous isopropanol under nitrogen atmosphere. The betaine 2-(*N*-*p*-methoxycinnamidopropyl-dimethylammonium)ethane-1-carboxylate (3) formed was characterized on the basis of spectral data.

Using this pure betaine chromatographic conditions were found out. Then we decided to attempt the derivatization procedure on the CAPB sample containing trace levels of SMCA. To establish the quantitative isolation of trace levels of SMCA, its subsequent derivatization and linearity of response, we spiked CAPB samples with SMCA and performed the analysis. For this experiment, we chose CAPB without any SMCA and this was established by ion chromatography. The spiked CAPB samples were passed through solid phase extractor and a definite quantity of filtrate was used for derivatization using *p*-methoxycinnamidopropyl-dimethylamine. The chromatographic conditions employed were the typical reverse phase conditions using C-18 column and 60% aqueous methanol as mobile phase. The isocratic condition was good enough for effecting excellent resolution. The detection was done at $\lambda_{\max}$ 280 nm.

The least-squares linear regression analysis of area count vs SMCA in CAPB obtained after chromatographing spiked samples over range of 10–50 ppm showed excellent linearity (Table 1) with correlation coefficient of 0.999. The replicate analysis, about 10 measurements of 10 ppm spiked sample, revealed good accuracy and precision with standard deviation of 0.19 ppm.

Table 1

Wt of CAPB sample g	Conc of spiked SMCA ppm	Area count	Found ppm
4.73	10	6228	9.15
5.02	20	13531	18.73
4.99	30	20537	28.60
5.01	40	27065	37.54

The comparison between results obtained from ion-chromatography and HPLC are shown in Table 2. In short, this new method gets validated by an established method based on ion-chromatography.

Table 2

SMCA spiked ppm	Found by IC ppm	Found by HPLC ppm
10	9.77	9.15
20	19.20	18.73
30	28.93	28.60
40	39.14	37.54

In summary, this method is useful for analyzing SMCA and similar types of molecules (sodium 3-chloro-2-hydroxypropylsulfonate) from a variety of surfactants, such as cocoamidofobetaine, alkyl ether carboxylates and alkanol ether carboxylates. It uses conventional HPLC technique with UV-detection and has good accuracy and precision.

The only limitation of this method is relatively long derivatization time of about six hours. Nevertheless, it is still an useful procedure for routine analysis.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Varian Cary-50 spectrophotometer and NMR spectra on a Varian 300 MHz instrument. Liquid chromatographic analysis was performed on Varian - Prostar 240, a ternary gradient system equipped with ChromSpher-C8 column (reverse phase) and UV/vis dual wavelength detector Prostar 345. Varian's MicroPak MCH-10 and ChromSphere-C8 (for reverse phase) were employed. Star chromatography workstation software (Varian Associates, USA) was used for data processing and quantification. The ion chromatography was performed on DX-500 Ion Chromatography equipped with a quaternary gradient pump GP 40 and a conductivity detector CD 20 (Dionex Corporation, Sunnyvale, California, USA). The eluent path and all other components in direct contact with the eluent were made up of an inert material, poly ether ether ketone (PEEK). The anion exchanger IonPacAS12A and anion self-regenerating suppressor ASRS-Ultra were chosen for SMCA analysis.

All HPLC grade solvents were used for chromatography, synthesis and extraction. Sodium monochloroacetate (BASF), *N,N*-dimethylaminopropyl-diamine (Hoechst), *p*-methoxycinnamoyl chloride (Aldrich) and cocoamidopropylbetaine (Galaxy Surfactants Ltd, commercial) were used.

p-Methoxycinnamidopropyl-dimethylamine: To a stirred solution of *N,N*-dimethylpropyl-diamine (102.0 g, 1.0 mol) in dichloromethane (500 ml), a solution of *p*-methoxycinnamoyl chloride (196.0 g, 1.0 mol) in dichloromethane was added slowly and the reaction was continued at room temperature for 2 h. The mixture was then washed with aq

Note

NaOH (200 ml; 20.0%). The organic layer was dried over anhyd. sodium sulfate. The removal of solvent using a rotary evaporator afforded the *p*-methoxycinnamidopropyl dimethylamine (235.0 g) as colourless solid, m.p. 80° (Found : C, 69.00; H, 8.80. C₁₅H₂₂O₂N₂ calcd. for : C, 68.70; H, 8.40%); λ_{max} (ε) 290 nm (26600), ν_{max} 1660 (CO of amide), 3300 cm⁻¹ (NH); ¹H NMR δ (300 MHz, CDCl₃) 1.73 (2H, p, *J* 6.6 Hz), 2.26 (6H, s), 2.42 (2H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz), 3.45 (2H, q, *J* 6.0 Hz), 3.81 (3H, s), 6.27 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 6.86 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.43 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.53 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz); ¹³C NMR δ (125 MHz, CDCl₃) 26.64, 39.15, 45.05, 55.27, 58.28, 114.22, 119.27, 127.80, 129.23, 139.70, 160.74, 166.47.

2-(N-p-Methoxycinnamidopropyl-N,N-dimethylammonium)ethane-1-carboxylate : To a solution of *p*-methoxycinnamidopropyl dimethylamine (4.52 g, 0.017 mol) in aq. isopropanol (IPA : H₂O, 10 : 05), sodium monochloroacetate (1.95 g, 0.017 mol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred under nitrogen at 80° for 6 h. The completion of reaction was ensured by quantitative liberation of chloride ion. The solvents were removed under reduced pressure and the dry solid left behind was washed with dichloromethane to remove traces of unreacted *p*-methoxycinnamidopropyl dimethylamine. The betaine (5.30 g, 0.017 mol) containing one equivalence of sodium chloride was obtained as colourless solid : λ_{max} (water) (ε) 307 nm (23600), ν_{max} (KBr) 1640–1665 (carbonyl of amide and carboxylate), 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH of amide); ¹H NMR δ (300 MHz, CDCl₃) 1.73 (2H, p, *J* 6.6 Hz), 2.26 (6H, s), 2.42 (2H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz), 3.45 (2H, q, *J* 6.0 Hz), 3.81 (3H, s), 6.27 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 6.86 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.43 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.53 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz).

Solid phase extraction, derivatization and chromatography : CAPB (5.0 g) was diluted with distilled water (25 ml) and the solution was passed through three solid phase extractors (Accubond C18, J & W Scientific, USA). To a definite quantity of this filtrate (about 3.0–4.0 g), *p*-methoxycinnamidopropyl dimethylamine solution (1.0%; 1.0 ml) in IPA and water (10 ml) were added. The mixture was stirred at 70–80° in an oil-bath for 6 h under the blanket of nitrogen. After 6 h of stirring, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and the volume made up to 50 ml with distilled water. 20 μl of this solution was used for HPLC using the following conditions : column : Chrom Spher C18; mobile phase : 60% aqueous methanol; flow rate : 1.0 ml/min; detection at 280 nm

Analysis of SMCA in CAPB by anion-exchange chroma-

tography : About 5.0 ml of 20–25 times diluted sample was passed through solid phase extractor to remove surfactant molecules. The filtrate thus obtained was passed through Ag-cartridge (J & W Scientific, USA) to remove the chloride ions and then chromatographed using following conditions : anion exchanger. IonPac AS12A with AG12A guard column; mobile phase : 10 mN NaOH; eluent flow rate : 1.5 ml/min; background conductivity suppressor : ASRS-Ultra (4 mm); current required for electrolysis of water : 50 mA; regenerant flow rate : 5.0 ml/min

References

- 1 A L L Hunting in "Encyclopedia of Conditioning Rinse Ingredients", ed A L L Hunting, Micelle Press, London, 1987, p 125
- 2 X Domingo in "Amphoteric Surfactants", ed E G Lomax, Surfactant Science Series, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1996, Vol 59, p 75
- 3 G W Femley, *J Am Oil Chem Soc*, 1978, 55, 98
- 4 Cosmetic, Toiletory and Fragrance Assc Inc, Final report on the safety assessment of cocoamidopropylbetaine, *J Am Coll Toxicol*, 1991, 10, 33
- 5 E G Lomax, Ref 2, pp 158-159
- 6 H H Beh and K C James, *Cosmet Toilet*, 1977, 92, 21
- 7 G Barker in "Surfactants in Cosmetics", ed M M Reieger, Surfactant Science Series, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1985, Vol 16, pp 251-292
- 8 J G Dominguez, F Balaguer, J L Parra and C Pelejero, *Int J Cosm Sci*, 1981, 3, 57
- 9 J G Weers, J F Rathman, F U Axe, C A Crichlow, L D Folland, D R Scheuing, R J Wiersema and A G Zielske, *Longmuir*, 1991, 7, 854
- 10 "Chemical Products Desk Reference", compiled by M Ash and I Ash, Edward Arnold, 1990, p 1090
- 11 "DIN Safety Data Sheet on Dimethylpropylamine", BASF, 1989
- 12 "Akzo Nobel Safety Data Sheet on Sodium Monochloroacetate", 1990
- 13 N M Koshti, S D Naik and N R Pai, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 2002, 79, 450
- 14 M Cetinkaya, *Parfum Kosmet*, 1991, 72, 816
- 15 M Humbert and A Hernandez, 'Determination of Monochloroacetate, Dichloroacetate and Glycolate in Betaine', '4th World Surfactant Congress', Barcelona, 1996
- 16 T M Schmitt in "Analysis of Surfactants", ed T M Schmitt, Surfactants Science Series, Marcel Dekker, 1992, Vol 40, pp 127-166
- 17 N Buschmann, A Kruse and R Schultz, *Comun J Com. Esp. Deterg*, 1992, 23, 317
- 18 N M Koshti, A H Jawale, B B Parab, S D Naik, M D Moghe, T S Jadhav and S S Nashte, US Pat Appl Nos FPAA 125 and FPAA 127, (2001)